

Estimation Techniques for Sample Project – Acoustical Ceilings, Drywall, Structural Concrete, and Rebar with Sample Proposal

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Abstract

This paper describes a fictional commercial construction project that involves building a 3,600 square-foot real estate office, which will include 13 offices, two conference rooms, two single-occupancy restrooms, a kitchen area, lobby, and janitor's closet. The project involves installing acoustical ceilings throughout, except for three rooms with drywall ceilings, and constructing the concrete foundation, which includes a continuous footer, stem wall, four-inch unreinforced slab, and thickened slab. The purpose of this study is for use as a training guide for construction management students. It includes a mock proposal with exclusions and clarifications, as well as a detailed discussion of takeoff and estimation techniques for the given trades.

The main concern for the project is the lack of material specification, and the suggestion is to wait for a response to the RFI requesting specifications and additional clarifications before submitting the proposal. The concrete subcontractor's mobilization will occur at the beginning and end of the project, and the acoustical ceilings will be installed in the final mobilization. The profit margins suggested are 20% for concrete and 20-25% for ceilings. This estimate does not include general requirements or administrative overhead costs.

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Michael Grubb

704 N Ashley St

Tampa, FL 33618

(813) 219-3042

September 3, 2021

Terry M. Smith
Ogden Development
P.O. Box 1256
Ogden, UT 84403

Dear Mr. Smith:

Let this letter serve as a formal notice of our intention to bid the concrete and finishes scope of the Real Estate Office project. We agree to comply with all of the terms laid out in the Request for Proposal, due date, and bid documents for this project.

Inclusions for this bid:

- Concrete
 - Slab on grade, 4"
 - Continuous footers
 - Vapor barrier
 - Stem wall
 - Rebar
- Finishes
 - Acoustical Ceilings
 - Insulation
 - Drywall
 - Interior/Exterior Paint
 - Ceramic tile on wall and floor of restroom, cove base
 - Carpet flooring with 4" rubber base
 - Bathroom accessories and partitions
 - Office Furniture
 - Exterior brick veneer
- General Conditions
 - Dumpster

- Portable toilets
- Temporary power
- Permits

Exclusions for this bid:

- Life safety/fire suppression
- Interior/exterior doors
- Windows
- Wood framing
- Gutters
- All MEP work
- Light fixtures
- Plumbing fixtures
- Grading
- Survey
- Temporary fence
- Dewatering/silt fence/erosion control
- Anything not explicitly listed above

Schematic pricing and timeframe:

- Slab/Foundation
 - \$5/SF
 - 14 days
- ACT
 - \$4.50/SF
 - 10 days
- Insulation/Drywall
 - \$3.25/SF
 - 12 days
- Interior/exterior paint
 - \$4.50/SF
 - 6 days
- Flooring
 - \$11/SF
 - 9 days
- Exterior veneer
 - \$24/SF
 - 18 days

Schematic pricing is subject to finish selections, of course.

Please contact me directly with any questions and kindly include me in any addenda or RFI responses that are published. I can be reached at (813) 219-3042 or michael.grubb@hemmingwayconstruction.com. I look forward to submitting a competitive bid and working with your team on this project.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'M. Grubb', written in a cursive style.

Michael Grubb
President

Michael Grubb
704 N Ashley St
Tampa, FL 33618
(813) 219-3042

September 2, 2021

Terry M. Smith
Ogden Development
P.O. Box 1256
Ogden, UT 84403

Dear Mr. Smith:

Hemingway Construction Group is a commercial general contractor with extensive experience building commercial office buildings. Serving the greater Tampa Bay area, our service area stretches down the west coast from Pasco County to Venice and east to Orlando. Please let this introductory letter serve to inform you of our interest in prequalifying with your firm in hopes of working together on the upcoming Real Estate Office project.

Hemingway Construction Group has experience in a variety of industries, including corporate-industrial and hospitality, but we have particular expertise in the construction of office buildings. As construction managers, we will serve as your partners during preconstruction, providing solutions such as cost estimating, value engineering options, sustainability analysis, constructability analysis, and field condition surveys. On every project, we put ourselves in the owner's corner and operate from the vantage point of our client.

Past Projects and Awards

Fanatics Corporate Headquarters, Tampa
2018 Excellence in Construction Gold Award (CISCA)
LEED Certified: Gold

ICOT Business Complex, Clearwater
2019 H. Dean Rowe FAIA Award of Excellence (AIA)
LEED Certified: Silver

Tampa Heights Union Office Building, Tampa
704 N Ashley St, Tampa, FL 33618 | 813.922.1101 | www.hemingwayconstruction.com
2020 Excellence in Construction Eagle Award (ABC)

LICENSED INSURED BONDED CBC1258172

Regarding the Real Estate Office project, my firm intends on submitting a formal Intention to Bid to your company soon for the concrete and finishes scope of this project, a timber-framed, single-story office building with a hipped roof, brick veneer, and timber structural posts.

Our scope would include pouring the monolithic slab with continuous footers at the interior support walls, continuous footers and stem wall around the perimeter of the foundation, and all structural rebar. While the building is in framing, we would install the exterior brick veneer and begin interior work after roof dry-in and MEP rough-in. The interior scope would include insulation and drywall, interior paint, flooring including ceramic tile on floors and walls of restrooms and carpet, acoustical ceilings, and providing the restroom accessories and office furniture. Depending on your needs, we could also pick up interior and exterior doors, windows, audio/visual equipment, or fire suppression equipment. I'll defer to your instruction to bidders for the full scope.

My firm would also be happy to work with you on VE options. At first glance, I think there may be some cost savings available by building exterior CMU walls instead of timber given the current price of lumber, and building the stem wall out of CMU instead of cast-in-place will certainly keep some of the costs down. If you decide to upgrade the vinyl windows to impact-rated windows, we can work with you on different interior finish options to help offset the cost. At every step we'll work with you to find cost savings without cutting corners.

Please visit HemingwayConstruction.com to view our full portfolio. We hope to be the preferred building partner on your next project. To discuss upcoming bids or if you have any questions about our firm, please contact me directly at (813) 219-3042 or michael.grubb@hemingwayconstruction.com.

Sincerely,

Michael Grubb
President

Takeoff and Estimate – Finishes

The scope of work for this estimate is ceilings, which includes acoustical ceiling tiles (ACT) and drywall. Both finishes are estimated based on square footage. While the ACT scope includes accounting for the linear footage of the perimeter to accurately estimate the grid and includes deducts for light fixtures and HVAC diffusers, the drywall ceiling is more straightforward, requiring less of a variety of materials.

Acoustical Ceilings

While the Real Estate Office drawings include the square footage for each room on sheet A1.0, I performed my own takeoff for accuracy. I also had to account for the linear footage in the perimeter of each room for some of the required materials, and the hallway square footage is not listed on sheet A1.0. In addition to accounting for the ceiling square footage, light fixtures and HVAC registers and grills sit inside of the suspended grid system and their square footage can be deducted from the ceiling tile count (Peterson & Dagostino, 2019). After taking off each room separately, I performed a count of all of the HVAC and light fixtures to deduct from my overall square footage (see Figure 1). The finish schedule on sheet A6.0 indicates that all rooms receive 2x2 ACT except for the restrooms and janitor's closet.

Figure 1

Ceilings Quantity Takeoff at Real Estate Office

① First Floor
1/8" = 1'-0"

Real Estate Office

Description	Label	Quantity	Unit	Length
Ceiling	2x2 ACT	2,303	sf	768
Ceiling	2x2 ACT	871	sf	343
Ceiling	Gypsum	76	sf	78
Deduct	2x2 Light Deduct	130	Count	

After completing my takeoff using Bluebeam, I entered all of the quantities into a spreadsheet to organize the data and estimate material needs (see Table 1). Since most of the rooms are square and indicate little waste, I used a ten percent waste factor for all areas except for the hallways. The hallway waste factor was increased to 20 percent due to the amount of cutting required by centering one tile in a four-foot width.

Table 1*Ceilings Takeoff Worksheet*

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Ceilings Takeoff Worksheet					
2		LF	SF	Waste	Total SF	Total LF
3	ACT	768	2303	0.10	2533	845
4	ACT (Hallway)	343	871	0.20	1045	412
5	Gypsum		76	0.70	129	
6						
7	ACT Deduct					
8		Count	SF/Panel	Total		
9		130	4	520		
10						
11	Totals:	SF	LF			
12	ACT	3060	1256			
13	Gypsum	129				
14						
15						
16	Material					
17	2x2 Panels	765	Tiles			
18	12' Mains	64				
19	4' Tees	382				
20	2' Tees	382				
21	Wall Angle	105				
22	Wire Hanger	2	Bundles			
23	Greenboard 4x8	5	Sheets			
24	Drywall Tape	1	Roll			
25	Joint Compound	1	Gallon			
26	Drywall Screws	1	box			

The ACT system includes 2x2 ceiling panels, 12-foot main runners, 4-foot and 2-foot cross tees, wall angle, and hanger wire (Peterson & Dagostino, 2019). By dividing the square footage of the ceiling panel, four, by the total square footage of the area after accounting for waste and deducts, 3,060, there are 765 ceiling tiles needed for this building. Ceiling tiles are sold by the carton, not by the piece (Armstrong, 2021). However, because there is not a specification for material, it is not possible to estimate the number of cartons needed, as square

footage per carton varies with different tiles. For 3,060 square feet, 64 main tees, 382 4-foot cross tees, and 382 2-foot cross tees are required (USG, 2021). Wall angle, which comes in 12-foot lengths, can be estimated by dividing the linear footage of the room perimeters, 1,256, by 12, to get 105 pieces. Again, these pieces are sold by the carton, so a specification is necessary to estimate the number of cartons. Hanger wire is required every four feet on center on the main runners (MikeArmstrong Ceilings, 2018). Sixty-four main runners times their length, 12, gives a total linear footage of 768. Dividing that number by four equals 192, the number of hanger wires needed for this project. Hanger wires are sold in bundles of 140 pieces, so two bundles are required.

Drywall

Because the drywall ceiling is located in restrooms and a janitor's closet where moisture may be an issue, I am estimating greenboard, a moisture-resistant drywall. One method of estimating drywall materials is to divide the area of the ceiling by the area of the drywall sheet to produce the number of sheets needed (Peterson & Dagostino, 2019). A four-foot by eight-foot drywall sheet has an area of 32 square feet. Using this formula, the total area for all three rooms is 76 square feet, divided by 32 yields three sheets needed. In practice, however, that is not an accurate estimate.

Looking at the sizes of the room, I have determined that there are two rooms that are 5'-7" by 5' and one room that is 3'-7" by 5' (see Figure 2). A single sheet of 4'x8' drywall will be sufficient for the smaller room, but the larger rooms are going to need more than a single sheet. Three sheets might be sufficient, but leave little room for waste. Therefore, I set my waste factor at a robust 70 percent to yield five sheets in the estimate. With such a small area, the inflated waste factors give me an allowance of two sheets per larger room and a single sheet for the

smaller room. According to Peterson and Dagostino (2019), drywall tape, joint compound, and drywall screws are also figured into the drywall estimate. Because the square footage is so small in these rooms, each item has a quantity of one on this estimate.

Figure 2

Room Measurements of Ceilings Receiving Gypsum Finishes

Summary

Acoustical ceiling tile requires a number of measurements for an accurate estimate: square footage, perimeter, and deductions for ceiling fixtures. Waste factor is also important to consider, as some areas, like the hallway, might require three tiles in each section because of the placement, and square footage alone will not account for the correct tile count. Similarly, drywall ceilings must be considered in regard to how the material will fit in the space. In the example provided by the Real Estate Office project, square footage alone will not yield the correct material estimate. Waste factors must account for the installation conditions specific to the project in order to produce accurate estimates. In addition to the main materials, such as ceiling tiles, grid, and drywall, ancillary materials must be accounted for to round out the estimate. Those materials include wire hangers, drywall tape, joint compound, and screws.

Finishes Basis of Estimate

To complete this estimate, I had to assume specifications for material. Since there is no finish schedule, I will qualify my estimate with these assumptions. I chose Armstrong Cortega tile with a tegular reveal which is budget friendly while still providing a finish suitable for offices. The grid system for a tegular tile is Armstrong Suprafine with a 9/16" reveal. The material costs, provided by Lowe's, are based on carton costs (see Table 1). The drywall is priced per sheet and the overall material order includes delivery to the job site. With 8' ceilings, no additional equipment is needed to unload or install the material.

Table 1

Material Costs for Acoustical Tile and Drywall Ceiling Systems

Material Costs						
Material Description	Unit Cost	Quantity	Subtotal	Tax	Total	
Armstrong Cortega 2x2 Tegular (64 sf/ctn)	\$ 98.67	12	\$ 1,184.04	\$ 88.80	\$ 1,272.84	
Armstrong Suprafine 12' Mains (240 LF)	\$ 290.57	4	\$ 1,162.28	\$ 87.17	\$ 1,249.45	
Armstrong Suprafine 4' Cross Tee (60 pcs)	\$ 258.43	7	\$ 1,809.01	\$ 135.68	\$ 1,944.69	
Amrstrong Suprafine 2' Cross Tee (60 pcs)	\$ 114.60	7	\$ 802.20	\$ 60.17	\$ 862.37	
Armstrong 9/16" Wall Mould (360 LF)	\$ 159.11	4	\$ 636.44	\$ 47.73	\$ 684.17	
12 Gauge Pre-Tied Hanger Wire (200 pcs)	\$ 108.52	2	\$ 217.04	\$ 16.28	\$ 233.32	
ToughRock Moisture Resistant Drywall (5/8x4x8)	\$ 13.98	5	\$ 69.90	\$ 5.24	\$ 75.14	
Sheetrock Joint Tape (250 LF)	\$ 2.37	1	\$ 2.37	\$ 0.18	\$ 2.55	
Sheetrock Pre-Mixed Joint Compound (4.5 gal)	\$ 14.97	1	\$ 14.97	\$ 1.12	\$ 16.09	
Drywall Screws #6 5/8"	\$ 7.48	1	\$ 7.48	\$ 0.56	\$ 8.04	
Delivery					\$ 80.00	
					\$ 6,428.66	

The crew composition is based on two mobilizations. Typically, the ceiling grid must be installed prior to any other trades, such as electricians and plumbers, finishing their work. Once the light fixtures have been installed along with any other above-ceiling work, the second mobilization will encompass tile installation. The ceiling system production rates are as follows,

assuming one person for one day: 300 hanger wires, 600 square feet of grid, 300 linear feet of wall angle, and 800 square feet of tile (grid ninja, 2010; Hill, 2007). 1,100 square feet of drywall can be installed by one person in one day (Tim0282, 2008). My total labor estimate was about fifteen labor days, which includes ten days for the grid and drywall in the first mobilization and five days for the tile installation. The crew composition includes a two-person crew for the first mobilization over five days with a single person returning for the tile installation over an additional five-day period. Because this is a smaller job, just over three thousand square feet, providing manpower to complete the job sooner becomes unfeasible, as the installers would be in each other's way as well as the way of other trades finishing their work.

According to the *Occupational Employment and Wage Statistics* (2020), ceiling mechanics and drywall installers both have a national mean hourly income just under twenty-five dollars. For an eight-hour shift, that is a total of \$200 per person per day. While the drywall ceiling and hanger wire will likely only take an experienced estimator a few hours each to install, none of my labor estimates account for less than one day of labor. This provides a built-in cushion for waste in my labor estimate.

My total estimate comes to \$11,314.39 (see Table 2), which includes all material and labor, with profit set to 20%. Given that the material includes appropriate waste factors, the labor estimate is slightly padded and assumes production rates on the lower side, and the job is marked up a healthy 20%, there are no additional negative contingencies that I am accounting for. The proposal will include furnishing material and labor for the ACT and drywall ceilings and will qualify the fact that the drawings did not provide a material specification. The submittal process will ensure that the owner approves of my choices prior to ordering. The drawings show batt insulation above the ceiling system, which will be excluded on this proposal. An RFI will clarify

whether that should be included in the ACT scope. The proposal will also exclude applying acoustical sealant along the wall angle, as that has not been specified.

Table 2

Estimate Total

Material	\$6,428.66	
Labor	\$3,000.00	
Profit and Overhead	\$1,885.73	20%
Total Estimate	\$11,314.39	

Takeoff and Estimate - Structural Concrete, and Rebar

The scope of work for this estimate is concrete, which includes the 4” slab, thickened slab, continuous footer, and stem wall. The concrete estimate includes labor, machinery, and material, which includes rebar as well as concrete.

Concrete Material

For this project, there are three specific takeoffs to consider: the 4” slab, continuous footer and stem wall, called out in detail 3/A5.1, and the thickened slab, shown in detail 4/A5.1. Estimating the slab was a matter of taking off the entire area shown in S1.0, while the thickened slab was a linear footage measurement of the two bisecting lines and the continuous footer and stem wall was a measurement of the perimeter of the foundation (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Slab, Thickened Slab, Continuous Footer, and Stem Wall Takeoff

These square footage and linear footage measurements were used along with the height and width details shown in sheet A5.1 to determine the total cubic yardage of concrete required for the foundation. According to the National Ready Mixed Concrete Association (2020), the national average for concrete is \$125 per cubic yard, which includes boom pumps. As such, the estimate for the concrete material on this project is \$10,625.00 without markup. The total concrete material required based on these measurements was 85 cubic yards, including a five per cent waste factor.

Rebar Material

Rebar take-offs are performed by the linear foot and include the number of bars, lengths, and pieces (Peterson & Dagostino, 2019). Rebar specifications are found on details 3/A5.1 and

4/A5.1 for the foundation wall and thickened slab. The rebar at the foundation wall, for example, includes three pieces of #4 rebar at the continuous footer, four pieces of #4 rebar at the stem wall, a #4 L-shaped dowel every 16" off center tying in the stem wall to the footer, and a piece of 18"x18" #4 rebar every 16" off center tying in the stem wall to the slab. According to *1/2 in. x 1 Ft. #4 Rebar (6-Per Bundle)*, (2021), #4 rebar is \$2.31 per linear foot, including tax. That price is included in my steel takeoff (see Table 1), along with the anchor bolts shown in detail 4/A5.1. Labor for rebar is included in the concrete pricing. Rebar reinforcement is not required for 4" slabs (Admin, 2018). Since no wire mesh is shown in the structural drawings at the slab, it is excluded from this estimate.

Table 1

Rebar Quantity Takeoff Worksheet

Rebar	Qty		LB/FT	LF	Price	Total	Weight
Continuous Footer	3	#4 continuous rebar	0.0668	250	2.31	\$ 1,732.50	50.1
Continuous Footer	16" OC	#4 Rebar	0.0668	294.822563	2.3	\$ 678.09	19.6941472
Stem Wall	4	#4 rebar	0.0668	250	2.31	\$ 2,310.00	66.8
Stem Wall	16" OC	#4 L-shaped dowel	0.0668	166.6666667	2.31	\$ 385.00	11.1333333
Thickened Slab	2	#4 continuous rebar	0.0668	140	2.31	\$ 646.80	9.352
Thickened Slab	16" OC	5/8"x12" anchor bolts		140	3.096	\$ 650.16	
Slab						N/A	
						\$ 6,402.55	

Equipment

The only equipment that this estimate accounts for is a mini excavator to excavate the perimeter for the continuous footer and stem wall. Boom pumps and any slab finishing equipment are included in the concrete labor pricing. According to BigRentz (2021), the cost of a mini excavator for one month is \$1,400. Even though the footer excavation will take just a few days, I have accounted for a one-month rental in this estimate, since other trades, such as plumbing and electrical, will also need a mini excavator on site. My total equipment estimate

(see Appendix B) includes an allowance for fuel and a delivery and pickup charge, but assumes on-site labor will operate the equipment.

Labor

Concrete slab labor is estimated at \$2.50 per square foot, while the continuous footer is \$30 per linear foot (*How Much Does It Cost to Pour a Concrete Slab? (Tampa, FL), 2021*).

While these rates are slightly higher than rates I am familiar with working with commercial subcontractors, any overage, as long as it is not excessive, provides a comfortable amount of padding in my estimate. This labor rate includes operating machinery, setting form boards, pouring and finishing concrete, and placing rebar and anchor bolts.

Project Findings

The concrete and finishes estimate includes all material, equipment, and labor required to install the finished ceilings and structural concrete. The material estimate for the ceilings includes twelve cartons of Armstrong Cortega 2x2 tegular tile, four cartons of 9/16" Armstrong Suprafine mains, 7 cartons each of 4' and 2' cross tees, and two bundles of hanger wire. The drywall ceiling material includes five sheets of 5/8" x 4' x 8' moisture-resistant drywall, one roll of joint tape, one 4.5-gallon container of joint compound, one five-pound box of drywall screws, and delivery fees. Labor for the ceilings is estimated at fifteen days and the total cost, excluding profit, is \$9,428.66.

The concrete estimate includes 85 yards of concrete for the 4" slab, thickened slab, continuous footer, and stem wall. A mini-excavator is included in the estimate for one month while boom pumps are figured into the concrete material costs. A variety of #4 rebar as well as 5/8" x 12" anchor bolts are also included in this estimate. Including labor, which is estimated by

the square and linear foot, material, equipment, and delivery, the total cost for the concrete, excluding profit, is \$42,615.00.

Basis for Estimate

This project did not include a project manual, specifications sheet, or material legend. Therefore, specific material had to be assumed. For the ceilings, the Armstrong products were chosen to supply a nice finished look for a professional office building at a budget price. The drywall material was assumed given the application in the restroom and janitor's closet. Furnishing material and labor as specified in the estimate is included. Any material not mentioned in the estimate, including batt insulation, aluminum-capped grid, acoustical sealant, and cement fiber board, is excluded.

For the concrete scope, anchor bolts embedded in the concrete are included. The concrete was not specified, so the estimate assumes 3,000 PSI with a medium broom finish. Wire mesh for the slab and grading have been excluded. Grading and dewatering have been excluded. It is assumed a graded building pad will be provided for us.

General requirements, such as surveying, permitting, temporary power, portable toilets, and dumpsters have been excluded. Administrative overhead, such as salaries for the accountant and project manager, have not been included in this estimate but should be added to the final proposal. Any scope of work not fully outlined in the proposal will be excluded and 40-hour work weeks excluding nights and weekends included. Finally, as a matter of course, union labor and Davis-Bacon prevailing wages are excluded, although they do not pertain to this project.

Presentation for Management

This project is a 3,600 square-foot real estate office with thirteen offices, two conference rooms, two single-occupancy restrooms, kitchen area, lobby, and janitor's closet. The scope of

work includes acoustical ceilings throughout with drywall ceilings in three rooms and the concrete foundation which consists of a continuous footer, stem wall, four-inch unreinforced slab, and thickened slab.

The main concern for this bid is a lack of material specification. Assumptions were made in material selection for a pricing exercise in order to complete the preliminary estimate. However, without a material schedule or project manual, we have no way of knowing if we are bidding apples to apples with our competitors, and that could potentially place us at a disadvantage for a competitive bid. It is important to document all assumptions (Green, 2006). An RFI will then need to be submitted requesting specifications, finish selections, and additional clarifications. I suggest we wait for that response before submitting our proposal.

For the concrete scope grading and dewatering have been excluded. For the ceilings acoustical sealant and drywall grid have been excluded. An additional consideration for the ceiling proposal is proper sequencing and the number of mobilizations. Because this is such a small project, profit and labor costs are very tight and there is little room for error. If we are asked to mobilize and rooms are not ready for full installation, additional mobilization costs will quickly eat away at the profit.

As the potential concrete and finish subcontractor, our mobilizations will occur at the beginning and end of the project, with no work in the middle. The first mobilization will be to form and pour the continuous footer. That will require arranging for the equipment delivery: first the excavator then the boom pumps. While we have an allowance in the estimate for a mini excavator for a month, I would see if the general contractor (GC) will provide the equipment for our use, since electricians and plumbers will be on site just before us digging trenches while the site is in subrough.

The continuous footer is poured just before the stem wall. After forming the footer with wood forms and placing the rebar, the concrete is poured and leveled (Hendron, 2016). The next day the wood forms can be removed from the footer and used to form the stem walls. The form boards are shored for support, additional rebar inserted, and more concrete poured to form the wall around the perimeter of the site (Hendron, 2016). The areas that will have the two thickened slabs will have already been excavated. The slab and the thickened slab will be monolithic, which is poured in one step instead of pouring the thickened slabs separately like the continuous footer, thus saving time (*Monolithic Slab*, n.d.). The slab will receive a medium broom finish and be left to cure. Care must be taken to keep the area moist or shaded from the sun to prevent cracks.

The next mobilization will occur toward the end of the project when we return to install the ceilings. The grid will be installed after the drywall has been painted and just before the electricians are ready for rough-in. Hanger wires will be attached to the trusses using eye bolts and tied to the 12' main runners. Wall angle will attach to the drywall with drywall screws after using a laser level to mark the placement, and cross tees attached to form the grid. While there are wall sections showing the acoustical ceiling attachment, there are no details showing how the finished drywall ceiling in the restrooms and janitor's closet are to be attached, nor are ceiling heights shown in the RCP. The estimate assumes 8-foot ceiling heights per sections on sheet A3.0. Moisture-resistant drywall is suggested for the application in this project. Drywall screws will be countersunk and then filled with joint compound and sanded smooth (*How to Drywall a Ceiling*, 2021). The seams are taped, mudded, and sanded to create a finished surface (*How to Drywall a Ceiling*, 2021). The plans did not specify a finish, so orange peel is assumed.

For the concrete scope, 38 cubic yards of concrete, 144 pounds of rebar, and 680 anchor bolts are needed. The cost for this scope, including material, waste, labor, and equipment, is \$42,615. The ceiling scope will require 12 cartons of tile, five sheets of drywall, four cartons of main runners, seven cartons each of four-foot and two-foot tees, four cartons of wall angle, two bundles of hanger wire, a container of joint compound, a roll of joint tape, and a box of drywall screws. The total cost for this scope including material and labor is \$9,428.66.

I initially set the profit for concrete at ten percent and the ceilings at twenty percent for a total profit of \$6,147.23 for approximately 165 labor days of work. However, these profit decisions were initially made assuming that we would bid a larger scope of work. According to Peterson and Dagostino (2019), five to ten percent profit is reasonable on a large job, but 20 to 25 percent is more in line with a small one. My suggestion is to raise the concrete profit to twenty percent for a total job profit of \$10,408.73. Note that these estimates do not include any general requirement costs, such as permitting, surveying, or dumpsters, and those should be excluded from the proposal. Also not included is administrative overhead, such as for accounting and project managers' salaries.

The final estimate breaks down as follows: The total cost is \$52,043.66. The total profit is \$10,408.73, for a total proposal of \$62,452.39, excluding additional overhead.

It is my opinion that we move forward with this proposal and take the following steps: submit an RFI for clarification on specifications and additional details that weren't evident in the drawings, adjust the proposal to incorporate additional overhead for the given duration, and settle on the final target profit margin.

Conclusion

The project is a 3,600 square-foot real estate office with thirteen offices, two conference rooms, two single-occupancy restrooms, a kitchen area, a lobby, and a janitor's closet. The scope of work includes acoustical ceilings throughout, with drywall ceilings in three rooms and the concrete foundation. However, the main concern is the lack of material specification, which makes it difficult to bid apples to apples with competitors. Therefore, an RFI should be submitted requesting specifications, finish selections, and additional clarifications. The project requires two mobilizations: the first for forming and pouring the continuous footer, and the second for installing the ceilings. Proper sequencing is crucial for the ceiling proposal to avoid additional mobilization costs. The total cost for the concrete and ceiling scopes is \$42,615 and \$9,428.66, respectively, with a suggested total profit of \$10,408.73. It is important to note that the estimates do not include any general requirement costs or administrative overhead.

References

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